

Road Accident Prediction and Classification on the basis of Machine and Deep Learning (RFCNN)

Sruthi K S

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
sruthiks2022b@mca.ajce.in

Merin Chacko

Department of Computer Application
Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, India
merinmanoj@amaljyothi.ac.in

Abstract—Road accidents are an inevitable part of everyday life. In most daily news reports, there is at least one occurrence of a traffic accident. The number of casualties and hence the damage done will be concerning depending on the severity of the accident. Every year, 1.2 million individuals are killed in traffic accidents. In Kerala alone, there will be 33296 incidents with apparent damage in 2021. It leads to a loss of lives and economic harm, and as a result, it is a sensitive issue that must be addressed. This study predicts the intensity of an accident occurring at a certain location and time using Machine Learning techniques.

Keywords—road accident prediction, ensemble model, RFCNN, traffic severity

I. INTRODUCTION

Because of the loosening of mobility limitations and offices coming out to call back staff, traffic volume on town roads surged in 2021, and road accidents increased by roughly 10% year over year. According to official data, the number of road accidents in town increased from 796 in 2020 to 874 in 2021. According to the month-by-month data, the most accidents happened in October and December, when public spaces were packed with people and normalcy was beginning to return before the Omicron-led third wave resulted in evening curfews. In addition, the number of fatal road accidents climbed by 10% from 347 in 2020 to 389 in 2021. While 375 people perished in deadly traffic accidents in 2020, 409 people died last year. When the fraction of fatal accidents is compared to the total number of accidents, the fatality ratio shows an increase. While roughly 43% of the incidents were deadly in 2020, it was a whopping 45 percent in 2021. Meanwhile, police and road safety officers blamed the uptick in accidents on an increase in traffic volume when the government eased limits on public movement in 2021. The monthly examination of the knowledge backs up these statements, revealing that the highest number of accidents happened in the second half of the year. The following are some of the major contributions made by this study:

- Random Forest (RF) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model is combined to form RFCNN.
- The experiment employs ML models such as the AdaBoost Classifier (AB), Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), Random Forest (RF), Extra Tree (ET), and Voting Classifier which are an

ensemble of LG (Logistic Regression) and SGD(Stochastic Gradient Descent) .

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The authors[1] compared statistical methods and machine learning models in predicting time for incident clearance. Deep learning models have also been employed by researchers in predicting the duration of road incidents.

S. Seid and Pooja[2] utilized the ANN to model injury severity of traffic accidents using classifying the injury severity into five different categories (no injury, possible injury, minor non-incapacitating injury, incapacitating and fatality)

This paper[3] used a Support Vector Machine and multi-layer perceptron to analyze road accidents. They explored only two variables that are speed and alcohol as a key contributor to road accidents. SVM outperformed with 94% accuracy. They claimed high-speed driving after drinking is the reason for the incident.

Authors[4] utilized CART(Classification and Regression Model) to analyze the rural traffic accidents in Iran. CART is utilized to find the most important variable that affects the severity of the accidents.

Authors[5] worked on the severity of traffic accidents in the United States using logistic regression. At probability cut-point 0.20 they obtained the model sensitivity and specificity were 40% and 98% respectively.

III. MOTIVATION

Every day, tens of thousands of people are killed or injured on the roads. Men, women, and children will never return home after walking, biking, or riding to school or work, or playing in the streets, leaving devastated families and communities. This study is significant because it can aid someone in estimating the intensity of an accident simply by looking at the characteristics of the data they offer. In this system, users create a model with the help of a dataset. The model is trained using this dataset, which was constructed with RFCNN. After that, the model is utilised to make predictions.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6791034

ISBN: 978-93-5607-317-3@2022 MCA, Amal Jyothi College of Engineering Kanjirappally, Kottayam

IV. METHODOLOGY

The focus of this research is to develop a ML model that can accurately determine if news is fake or authentic using the provided information. The severity of road accidents can be correctly predicted using an ensemble learning model that blends machine learning and deep learning models. RFCNN is a model that combines Random Forest (RF) and Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) models. This experiment demonstrates the usage of machine learning models such as Random Forest(RF), AdaBoost Classifier(AB), Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM), Extra Tree(ET), and Voting Classifier. The structure is as follows:

Figure 1: Proposed Methodology Diagram

The steps that require to be followed are:

1. Data Collection
2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing

5. Result

A. Data Collection: There are three csv files: accidents, casualties, and vehicles, as well as a fourth file with traffic statistics from 2000 to 2015. In two stages, RFCNN is applied to the US road accident dataset. Three files must be imported in order to analyze the data. In the first phase, the intensity of the accident is forecasted using all 48 features of the dataset. The RF classifier is used to calculate the top 20 features, and feature importance is used to train all models in the experiment's second portion to predict the severity of road accidents.

B. Data Pre-processing: Due to their varied origin, the majority of real-world datasets for machine learning are particularly sensitive to missing, inconsistent, and noisy data. Applying data mining algorithms to this noisy data would produce poor results since they would be unable to detect patterns. As a result, data processing is critical for improving overall data quality.

1. **Cleaning Data**—Cleaning data involves filling in missing values, smoothing noisy data, resolving inconsistencies, and removing outliers as purpose of data preprocessing.
2. **Data visualization and normalization**—As there are only a few columns to standardize, our machine learning methods will not be affected. If your ML method is not normalized, it can bias its performance, so it can be fixed as well.
3. **Data Splitting**— The data is then separated into two datasets: training and testing. Consider a few characteristics as predictions for your machine learning method. After that, we use the data we chose for training to train our model.

C. Machine Learning: The accident severity is predicted using machine learning algorithms. Different base learning models and classifiers are used in this research. The steps are:

1. **RF- Random Forest** is also a preferred ML algorithm that belongs to the supervised learning technique. it's supported the concept of ensemble learning.
2. **AdaBoost Classifier (AC)**- The AdaBoost algorithm, which stands for Adaptive Boosting, is a Boosting technique that can be utilized as an Ensemble Method in machine learning. It's termed so because weights are re-allocated at each instance, with higher values assigned to instances that are mistakenly categorized.
3. **Extra Tree Classifier (ETC)**- Extremely Randomized Trees Classifier is a type of ensemble learning technique that combines the outcomes of several de-correlated decision trees collected over the course of a "forest" to produce a classification result.
4. **Gradient Boosting Machine (GBM)**- The predictions from several decision trees are combined

using a Gradient Boosting Machine, or GBM, to get the final word predictions. Keep in mind that in a highly gradient boosting machine, the weak learners are all decision trees.

5. **Convolutional Neural Network (CNN)**- It is a type of image recognition and processing artificial neural network designed exclusively for pixel data processing.

V. BUILD MODEL

One of the main steps in the accident severity prediction is building model. The steps involved are:

1. Import the necessary packages and start data cleaning.

```
import datetime as dt
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import seaborn as sns
#from mpl_toolkits.basemap import Basemap
from sklearn.model_selection import TimeSeriesSplit
plt.style.use('ggplot')
%config InlineBackend.figure_format = 'retina'
import warnings
warnings.filterwarnings('ignore')

accidents = pd.read_csv('Accidents.csv', index_col='Accident_Index')
casualties = pd.read_csv('Casualties.csv', error_bad_lines=False, index_col='Accident_Index', warn_bad_lines=False)
vehicles = pd.read_csv('Vehicles.csv', error_bad_lines=False, index_col='Accident_Index', warn_bad_lines=False)
#general_info = pd.read_csv('ukTrafficADF.csv')
```

2. Then visualize the data.

```
plt.figure(figsize=(12,6))
accidents.Date_time.dt.dayofweek.hist(bins=7,rwidth=0.55,alpha=0.5,color='orange')
plt.title('Accidents on the day of a week', fontsize=30)
plt.grid(False)
plt.ylabel('Accident count', fontsize=20)
plt.xlabel('0 - Sunday, 1 - Monday, 2 - Tuesday, 3 - Wednesday, 4 - Thursday, 5 - Friday, 6 - Saturday', fo
```

3. As the dataset is in numeric values and the correlation between columns can be identified and normalized.

```
corr = accidents.corr()
plt.subplots(figsize=(20,9))
sns.heatmap(corr)

sns.distplot(accidents['Age_of_Driver']);
fig = plt.figure()
sns.distplot(accidents['Age_of_Vehicle']);
fig = plt.figure()
```

4. Splitting the data into training data and test data

```
# Split the data into a training and test set.
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(accident_ml.values, accidents['Accident_Severity'].values,
                                                random_state=99)
```

5. Initialize RandomForestClassifier.

```
random_forest = RandomForestClassifier(n_estimators=200)
random_forest.fit(X_train, y_train)
Y_pred = random_forest.predict(X_test)
random_forest.score(X_test, y_test)
acc_random_forest1 = round(random_forest.score(X_test, y_test) * 100, 2)
```

6. Then identify on test set and calculate the accuracy of the model.

```
Y_pred = grid_search.predict(X_test)
acc_random_forest1 = round(grid_search.score(X_test, y_test) * 100, 2)

sk_report = classification_report(
    digits=6,
    y_true=y_test,
    y_pred=Y_pred)
print("Accuracy", acc_random_forest1)
print(sk_report)
pd.crosstab(y_test, Y_pred, rownames=['Actual'], colnames=['Predicted'], margins=True)
```

There was not much of a difference between Accident severity 1 and 2. However, there was an increase in the accuracy of Accident severity 3a, which went from 75.1 percent to 85.8%.

VI. RESULT

Based on the provided dataset, the result shows that prediction is done using ML and a deep learning model RF and a Convolutional Neural Network named RFCNN. RFCNN's smart architecture is what makes it more efficient and accurate. The essential feature highlighted by RN may be used to calculate the cost of data gathering and the prediction performance of the models. Because the most critical element impacting the intensity of an accident is the gap between vehicles, road authorities can take reasonable precautions by looking at specific variables revealed by RF, as demonstrated.

VII. CONCLUSION

This study describes a strategy for predicting the severity of road accidents at a specific location and time. The model will be trained using characteristics such as speed limit, age, weather, vehicle type, light conditions, and day of the week. The severity levels are 1 (fatal), 2 (serious), and 3 (minor). This receives the user's input and delivers it to the RFCNN Machine Learning model, which is used to process it. With the input data, the model forecasts the severity of an accident that occurs at the user's specific location.

This model will play an important role in planning and management of traffic and would help us reduce a lot of road accidents in the future. The superiority in predicting accidental severity is depicted clearly using RFCNN which is revealed through the performance comparison of the models. There was a high increase in the complexity when compared with the models individually which will be further used for future. The proposed model can be used on the multi-domain dataset and hence its effectiveness and generalizability can be proved.

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